

Collaborative Support System In Relation To Teacher Teaching Motivation

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the relationship between the collaborative support system and teacher teaching motivation in public elementary schools in the Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. Moreover, considering the inclusion criteria in this research study, and using Raosoft Calculator, a sample size calculator, the qualified respondents were only 141 teachers out of 220 within the Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The findings revealed that the Collaborative Support System regarding Dialogue, Decision Making, Action Plan, and Evaluation was Extensive. Likewise, the extent of the teacher teaching motivation in terms of Welfare, Promotion, Growth Support, and Cultural Atmosphere was also extensive. The work environment was perceived as essential in the school community. Meanwhile, teacher efficacy was vast regarding motivation, students' performance, reinforcement, and persistence. Significant relationships exist between collaborative support systems and teachers' motivation to teach in public elementary schools in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, public elementary schools. All Domains in the collaborative support system significantly influenced the teachers' teaching motivation. The components of a collaborative support system are Dialogue, decision-making, action, and evaluation. Lastly, a similar or comparative study exploring other indicators was suggested to develop a collaborative support system, teacher teaching motivation, and publish this study in a reputable journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Collaborative Support system
2. teachers' teaching motivation
3. Laak North district
4. Division Davao de Oro

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1. Introduction

Teachers are crucial for acquiring opportunities, information, and inspiration. The most critical component of the school is to ensure that students are adequately prepared to achieve their objectives. They impact a student's path to learning and personal development as mentors and advisors in addition to being educators. Teachers play a vital role in students' lives by encouraging critical thinking, igniting curiosity, and instilling values that students carry with them for the rest of their lives. An effective support system that serves as a strategy and a progress indicator is essential to ensuring that every student has equitable access to excellent instruction. It affects students' academic performance, molds their study habits, and prepares them for future challenges. Teachers teach subjects and develop the next generation of leaders, innovators, and thinkers by creating a motivated learning environment. Likewise, a collaborative

learning system is a tool that facilitates knowledge sharing and joint learning between educators and learners. Students can use it to share information within a team or to collaborate on assignments in small groups. Through collaborative learning, students can learn new material and apply what they have learned to practical situations. In a global scenario, Pakistan's education system has encountered many challenges within its public schools, with a prominent issue being the deficiency in teachers' motivation. The Pakistani government is committed to providing its people with high-quality education. There has been a constant effort to use different tactics to reward the teachers. Despite the concerted efforts made by the government to incentivize teachers, their performance continues to fall short of the desired benchmarks, directly impacting student academic outcomes (Ramzan Khurram, 2023). In China, public junior middle schools are essential to the educational framework of Western China, with educators significantly contributing to the development of a high-quality education system. Improving teachers' motivational strategies is crucial for their professional growth. However, few investigations and studies adequately address the needs of schools in improving motivational strategies. Effective motivational strategies should be implemented by the needs of the teacher support system (Su Wang, 2023). The slow progress in scientific literacy has led policymakers and researchers to concentrate on educators, their training, and their motivation to participate in their profession (Ministry of Education, 2021), as cited. Additionally, this aligns with research demonstrating that educators play a crucial role in student learning. Motivation plays a key role in shaping student engagement and acceptance of the educational experience. Numerous studies indicate that motivated educators are crucial for fostering classroom environments that improve learning, well-being, and motivation (Govorova et al., 2020). In light of these issues, broad

international studies like the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) are able to bridge existing research gaps and offer meaningful guidance to policymakers, academics, and education professionals. Such studies assess how teaching practices, educational policies, and social as well as cultural conditions influence students' academic outcomes and emotional development (Kirsch Braun, 2020). They do so by analyzing a diverse range of variables related to students, educators, and schools. PISA assesses reading comprehension, mathematics, and scientific literacy, while also collecting data on the personal attributes of instructors and students, along with various school-level factors associated with student learning. This study utilizes data from the PISA survey to empirically analyze the effect of instructors' motivation on student performance. The national support system for teaching motivation is crucial for improving the quality of the teaching and learning process. Effective educators play a crucial role in improving student performance. The improvement of teacher quality is essential within various educational reform initiatives designed to enhance educational quality (Results-based Performance Management System Manual, 2018, as cited by Suárez-Mesa Gómez, 2024). According to Araneta et al., (2020), during the 2018-2019 academic year in the Division of Iloilo, a study was conducted to evaluate teachers' instructional quality and motivation, serving as a foundation for a professional development program supported by administrative assistance for educators. This was founded on the principle that effort correlates with performance. The school can address this by analyzing the factors that motivate teachers to implement effective instructional practices. Meador (2018) reported that a school leader has the authority to assist and empower teachers, which is essential for enhancing effectiveness and motivation, key factors in academic achievement. The Philippines has the potential to develop well-rounded

children through skilled educators who impart values, provide 21st-century skills, and facilitate national advancement and progress. In the regional context, a study was undertaken involving secondary school teachers in Northern Mindanao, highlighting the perception that public school educators are accountable for numerous responsibilities outside classroom instruction. This affects the provision of high-quality instruction to students. The agency's escalating demands, encompassing inclusive education, zero dropout rates, increased workloads, additional forms, and burdensome paperwork, undermine teachers' enthusiasm and capacity to succeed. The DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016, through its gazette, acknowledges that the caliber of instruction significantly impacts the quality of education. Consequently, the Department of Education publicly designate proficient teachers and facilitate educators' professional advancement in instruction. As Bao (quoted in Nair, 2020) notes, educational institutions frequently encounter considerable time limitations in providing instructional resources, technical infrastructure, and pedagogical assistance. Educators can recognize organizational support when offered various educational resources. Although organizational support is essential in academic institutions, insufficient administrative assistance might result in teacher demotivation. Furthermore, the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) investigated the pressures and demotivation experienced by public school instructors in Davao dis Oro and the implications for instructional quality. It was determined that multiple intricate and interrelated pressures exist. The instructors' workload is significant, as they often experience excessive demands due to many tasks (David, Albert, and Vizmanos, 2019). Furthermore, additional administrative help beyond what is now offered is necessary to alleviate their burden, allowing them to focus on teaching. The limits encountered nationwide raise significant apprehension

regarding the quality of education. Certain educators may perceive a lack of appreciation or value in the Laak area if they do not receive feedback, commendation, or incentives for their efforts. When confronted with inflexible regulations, procedures, or curricula, individuals may perceive a lack of autonomy in their work. They may see a deficiency of trust or support from their superiors, colleagues, or students. Educators may encounter inadequate working conditions or constrained educational funding. The researcher is tasked with understanding how the collaborative support system significantly influences and correlates with teacher motivation in teaching. Teaching motivation is crucial since it enhances student learning outcomes and instructor performance. Motivated kids are more inclined to exert effort, persevere, and exhibit creativity. Motivated educators are more inclined to be involved and excel in their performance. The emphasis on excellent teaching has intensified inside numerous education systems, necessitating an assessment of instructors' motivation to guarantee effective instruction and enhanced learning outcomes. This research aims to determine the precise state of teachers' motivation and examine the correlation between the support system available to instructors and their motivation to educate. The study seeks to elucidate the complex relationship between the collaborative support system and the teaching motives of educators in Laak, North District, and to comprehend how these elements influence the overall efficacy and quality of the teaching and learning process. The assistance provided to instructors in several ways reflects their motivation in the teaching process. This, in turn, significantly impacts the efficacy of teaching performance, enhancing the academic capabilities of the key beneficiaries, the pupils.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

*1.1.1. Collaborative Support Systems (CSS) in Education—*Collaborative support systems (CSS)—such as peer mentoring, team

teaching, and professional learning communities (PLCs)—enhance teacher motivation, instructional quality, and retention (Jones Carr, 2019; Johnson Kelley, 2020). When administrators support these systems with time, resources, and recognition, teachers report higher job satisfaction, professional growth, and autonomy (Brown Walker, 2019; Turner, 2020).

CSS positively impacts teacher morale by fostering shared accountability, reflective dialogue, and a culture of continuous improvement (Garcia Fernandez, 2020; Huang Rivera, 2021). However, successful implementation depends on contextual factors like leadership commitment, trust, and culture (Miller Scott, 2022; Thompson, 2020).

Challenges include resource constraints, resistance from educators used to solitary work, and weak administrative support (Bennett Cooper, 2021). Still, when designed around mutual respect and shared goals, CSS fosters inclusion, reduces professional isolation, and improves instructional consistency (Lefstein et al., 2020; Hontvedt et al., 2021).

1.1.2. Teacher Collaboration and Decision-Making—Teacher collaboration—through planning, peer observation, and shared decision-making—improves classroom practice and student outcomes (Spangler Yingst, 2023; Carroll et al., 2021). Involving teachers in school-level decisions promotes ownership, trust, and alignment with institutional goals (Musengamana et al., 2024; Kippers et al., 2018).

Collaborative action plans, such as the “Solution Summit” or Participatory Action Research (PAR), structure teamwork to foster innovation and professional capacity (Turner Sanatana, 2023; Van Oostveen, 2018). Studies show that purposefully scheduled collaboration improves instructional coherence and community engagement (Capobianco Feldman in Gordon, 2018).

1.1.3. Connected Professional Learning—Professional development is more effective

when it’s ongoing, content-focused, and embedded in daily practice. Models like Connected Professional Learning emphasize expert-led planning, curriculum alignment, and feedback (Rosenberg et al., 2020). Moving from isolated workshops to embedded coaching yields better teacher performance and student results.

1.1.4. Teaching Motivation and Welfare—Teaching motivation is linked to autonomy, competence, and relatedness, as explained in self-determination theory (Ryan Deci, 2018). Collaborative environments boost intrinsic motivation, reduce burnout, and increase retention (Garcia Fernandez, 2020; Kumari Kumar, 2023). However, lack of resources and administrative support can hinder these effects (Bennett Cooper, 2021).

Teacher welfare—including job security, recognition, and professional growth—directly influences motivation and effectiveness (Ashaba et al., 2022; Kulikowski Sedlak, 2020). Institutions that invest in intrinsic and extrinsic rewards foster more committed, effective educators.

1.1.5. Evaluation, Promotion, and Growth Support—Fair and transparent promotion systems are crucial for morale and equity. However, studies highlight concerns over favoritism and lack of protocol adherence (Mbokazi et al., 2022; Setlhare, 2019). Teacher participation in evaluation and promotion decisions improves legitimacy and staff alignment with school goals (Sadiq et al., 2019).

Growth support includes personalized professional development, feedback, and capacity building, especially when aligned with teacher interests and classroom contexts (Fullan, 2020; Muir et al., 2021). Personalized learning environments driven by teacher and student collaboration foster autonomy and skill development (Prain et al., 2018).

1.1.6. Cultural Atmosphere and School Climate—School culture—comprising values, norms, and relationships—greatly impacts

teaching effectiveness and learning outcomes (Ismail et al., 2022; Dimmock et al., 2021). Positive culture fosters trust, inclusion, and a strong sense of belonging. Schein’s model explains culture through artifacts (visible norms), espoused values (goals and principles), and underlying assumptions (unseen beliefs) (Ismail, 2021).

1.1.7. Collaborative Evaluation—Collaborative evaluation actively involves stakeholders in assessment processes, improving engagement, data relevance, and decision-making (Agulhas, 2022; Chehaib et al., 2023). Rooted in “evaluation voices” and community development, this model promotes shared understanding, diversity, and sustained improvement. It requires regular dialogue, alignment of terminology, and commitment to equity.

1.2. Synthesis—An analysis of the factors and their significance, particularly the impact of the collaborative support system on teacher motivation, summarizes the review of related literature. Additionally, researchers have found that factors influencing teachers’ motivation—whether self-determined or not—significantly impact their performance. To meet the needs of teachers, the administration must create policies and procedures that inspire them. Enhancing the educational system requires school administrators to ensure that teachers have access to adequate resources, including rewards, acknowledgment, open communication, and both emotional and ethical support, as well as competitive compensation. These measures help ensure both effective teaching and positive student learning outcomes. A collaborative support system significantly boosts teacher motivation by fostering a sense of community, reducing feelings of isolation, and providing opportunities for professional development. When educators collaborate, they can exchange ideas, resources, and support, which benefits students’ learning and increases their job satisfaction. Future studies must address these challenges by examining how collabora-

tive support systems can be tailored to various school environments and cultures. Moreover, more long-term research could clarify the long-term effects of cooperative efforts on teacher retention and motivation. Education professionals can enhance their strategies for assisting teachers and increasing their motivation by further investigating this relationship.

1.3. Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework—

These theories are pertinent to and corroborative of the ongoing research. Theoretical frameworks such as Bandura’s Efficacy Theory, Locus of Control Theory, Attribution Theory, and Self-Worth Theory offer valuable perspectives. Bandura’s (1982) self-efficacy theory, in particular, emphasizes the significance of individuals’ beliefs in their capabilities, which substantially influence the effort they exert, their perseverance, and the goals they pursue. Studies have shown that individuals with strong self-efficacy tend to be more driven and successful in achieving their goals. Additionally, self-efficacy is more closely linked to one’s perceived abilities and use of cognitive strategies than to actual skill levels when predicting achievement. Another avenue of investigation in the domain of motivation examines the locus of control phenomenon. The locus of control notion is a focus of further research in motivation. This hypothesis suggests that people tend to be more motivated when they believe they can influence their successes and failures (Eccles Wigfield, 2002). One perspective on control theory indicates that autonomy, together with competence and relatedness, is among the three core psychological needs. Eccles and Wigfield (2002) reported that Connell and Wellborn (1991) found a correlation between individual variability in fulfilling basic needs and variations in motivation levels. Attribution theory pertains to an individual’s beliefs about the factors that contribute to successful or unsuccessful performance. Various forms of attribution exist, including skill, effort, task, and luck. Attribution theory posits that

Fig. 1. The Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Study.

an individual’s attributions influence their motivation, contingent upon whether the reason is regarded as mutable and within their control. Innate ability is generally considered a stable characteristic that is difficult to change, whereas effort is within an individual’s control and can be modified as needed. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework, outlining the structure that guides this study. This section designates the collaborative support system as the inde-

pendent variable and teacher motivation as the dependent variable. The study highlights two main variables: the exogenous variable, collaborative support system, which encompasses dialogue, decision-making, action, and evaluation; and the endogenous variable, teacher motivation, measured through indicators such as welfare, evaluation, promotion, growth support, and cultural environment.

The first box serves as the study’s independent variable, connected by an arrow to the second box, which primarily serves as the dependent variable. The arrow indicates that the collaborative support system’s first variable directly relates to teacher-teaching motivation.

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—This research aimed to investigate the relationship between the collaborative support system and teacher motivation in the teaching context. This investigation sought to examine the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of the collaborative support system in terms of
 - (1) dialogue;
 - (2) Decision making;
 - (3) Action Plan; and
 - (4) Evaluation?
- (2) What is the extent of teacher-teaching motivations in terms of
 - (1) Welfare;
 - (2) evaluation and promotion;
 - (3) Growth Support; and
 - (4) Cultural atmosphere?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between a collaborative support system and teacher motivation to teach?

- (4) Which domain of the collaborative support system significantly influences teacher teaching motivation?

1.5. Hypotheses—This study tested the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. H01: There is no significant relationship between the collaborative support system and the teacher's teaching motivation. H02: None of the indicators of the collaborative support system significantly influences the teacher's teaching motivation.

2. Methodology

This chapter analyzes the research design, participant selection, instruments utilized, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques.

2.1. Research Design—To accomplish the study's objectives and collect relevant data, the researcher utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational approach. According to McCombes (2019), a research design or strategy is a structured plan developed to address research questions. This framework outlines the specific methods and procedures for gathering, analyzing, and interpreting data. Essentially, the research design explains the approach the researcher will use to examine the main problem, making it a key component of the research proposal. Bhandari (2020) stressed that quantitative research is characterized by its emphasis on measuring and analyzing data numerically. This methodology typically follows a deductive approach, prioritizing the testing of theories, and is influenced by empiricist and positivist perspectives. In contrast, non-experimental research does not involve altering an independent variable; instead, it involves observing and measuring variables as they exist naturally, without intervention from the researcher. The researcher believed a descriptive correlation method was effective for this research study. Through quantitative analysis, the researcher determined the relationship between collaborative support systems and teachers' teaching motivation, which was the most appropriate design for the topic.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher carefully followed the standard procedures outlined in the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly concerning the management of participants and data. Survey questionnaires, along with relevant supporting literature, were submitted for further evaluation. Maintaining integrity, safeguarding participants, and guaranteeing the responsible conduct of studies all depend on ethical considerations in research. These factors include potential harm, informed consent, confidentiality, and transparency. For instance, a survey researcher needs to obtain participants' informed consent by outlining the study's goal, disclosing any potential risks, and ensuring that participation is voluntary. Maintaining participant identities and data confidentiality involves keeping them safe from unwanted access or disclosure. Additionally, researchers must take precautions to minimize risks, be aware of potential physical and psychological harm, and ensure that research methods are transparent, including the reporting of truthful results and the citation of sources. After obtaining approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. The researcher secured written consent from participants after providing them with clear and comprehensive information about the study's purpose. This ensured that participants fully understood their involvement and could make an informed decision about taking part in the research. It was explicitly stated that participation in the study is voluntary for all participants. If someone declined to partici-

pate, the researcher did not compel them to do so. Furthermore, the researcher is vigilant in safeguarding the respondents' psychological welfare. Permission was secured from the participants. The researcher explained to them that the study aimed to explore how collaborative support systems relate to teacher motivation and their impact on primary teaching methods.

2.3. Research Respondents—The researcher set criteria for including respondents in the study, such as public elementary school teachers with more than three years of teaching service. The teacher-respondents agreed to participate in the study conducted by the researcher. The research participants effectively filled out the information requested in the structured research survey questionnaire administered by the researcher. Moreover, considering the inclusion criteria in this research study, the qualified respondents were only 141 teachers out of 220 within the Laak North District, Davao de Oro Division. Raosoft Calculator served as a sample size calculator in survey research, facilitating the determination of the necessary number of respondents to attain a specified level of accuracy. Sample size estimation is a critical consideration for researchers conducting research projects; however, it is frequently misunderstood or overlooked (Memon et al., 2020). The researcher used a Raosoft calculator to select and determine 141 samples from 220 qualified respondents in the Laak North District, Davao de Oro, specifically from public elementary schools.

2.4. Research Instrument—The survey questionnaire used in this study was adapted from a previous study and modified to suit the specific needs and context of the current study. This can involve adding, removing, or changing the content of questions. Moreover, the researcher used three sets of instruments in this study to ensure that the appropriateness of the study was adequately addressed. The questionnaire for the independent variable, collaborative

support system, was adapted and modified from the analysis of Researcher-made survey questionnaires by Woodland and Randall (2013) for collaborative support and Su and Wang (2023) for teachers' motivations. It would undergo validation by an expert and pilot testing to establish the reliability and validity of the survey instrument. The pilot testing would identify at least 30 respondents for the said purpose. The researcher would modify and adapt it to fit the demands of the population, and the study's objectives would serve as the instrument for the study. A survey questionnaire was suitable for this study as it enables the researcher to collect a substantial volume of data efficiently. Furthermore, by modifying the questionnaire, the researcher can customize the survey questions to align more closely with the study's objectives and the target population. Education professionals assessed the questionnaire utilized in this study. A pilot test was subsequently conducted to evaluate its validity and reliability. The reliability assessment of the original scale yielded a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.761. Respondents utilized the 5-point Likert scale to answer the questionnaire. This serves as a framework for assessing teachers' degree of collaborative support concerning their teaching motivations. The researcher employed various methods, descriptions, and interpretations. This study employed a 5-point Likert scale in its survey questionnaire. In the social sciences, particularly in educational research, the Likert scale is commonly used to measure individuals' attitudes, opinions, and perceptions regarding a specific topic. The widely used 5-point Likert scale allows respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with a statement by rating items on a five-point scale that ranges from "very extensive" to "not extensive". It was reasonable to use a Five-point Likert scale in this study because it offers a range of replies that can capture subtle differences in the thoughts or perceptions of the respondents. The scale makes it sim-

ple to tabulate and statistically analyze replies, facilitating data analysis. The validity and reliability of the data gathered are further enhanced by using a standardized scale, such as the 5-point Likert scale, which enables comparisons between various studies. The research instrument consists of two parts; the first part, adapted from Su Wang (2023), contains 18-item questions. The second part consisted of 20 items and

was adapted from Ramzan and Khurram (2023). For the independent variable, which was the collaborative support system, a modified and adapted questionnaire was taken from the study of Su Wang (2023); the questionnaire consists of 18 items. The Likert Scale below was used to assess the extent of the collaborative support system.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The collaborative support system of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The collaborative support system of teachers is often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The collaborative support system of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The collaborative support system of teachers is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The collaborative support system of teachers is never manifested.

For the dependent variable, teacher teaching motivation, a modified and adapted questionnaire from Ramzan and Khurram’s study

(2023), which consisted of 18 questions, was employed. The Likert scale below assessed the teachers’ teaching motivations.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher’s teaching motivations are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher’s teaching motivations are very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher’s teaching motivations are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher’s teaching motivations are rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher’s teaching motivations are never manifested.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The required data were collected using the following procedures: The researcher requested approval from the Dean of the Graduate School to proceed with the study. A request letter, accompanied by the Dean’s endorsement, was submitted to the School’s Division Superintendent for

approval. The researcher obtained permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of the Davao de Oro Division to survey the teacher respondents. The permission letter issued by the Schools Division Superintendent was provided to the school principals and district supervisor in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, to facilitate the ex-

ecution of the research study. The school principals and supervisor consented to the arrangement following an assessment of the standard safety protocols related to the research study conducted. Following approval, the researcher administered the research survey tool personally and collected the data. The researcher adhered to ethical standards throughout the study, complying with the standard study protocol assessment and standardized criteria, especially in managing the respondents and data. The principals secured a copy of the approved letter from the School Division Superintendent (SDS) to verify that the researcher conducted and collected the data from the study respondents. The data gathered was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially accordingly. The results of this study were analyzed and interpreted in light of the study's purpose. After the responses were retrieved and tallied, they were forwarded to the statistician for data treatment. The teachers' respondents from Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, have given their free will to participate or withdraw from the study without any form of consequence or penalties. The respondents provided their personal information relevant to the study, which

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the study's findings, which were thoroughly examined, analyzed, and interpreted.

3.1. Collaborative Support System in terms of Dialogue—Table 1 presents the data on the extent of the collaborative support system in terms of dialogue. The presentation is arranged from the highest to the lowest mean rating obtained: Faculty members consistently attend team meetings. (4.03); The topics for team discussions are scheduled in advance, documented, and shared with all teachers prior to the meeting (4.02). A comprehensive and pre-

was maintained strictly confidential and handled with the highest regard for data privacy. The research survey questionnaire lacked technical terminology, ensuring comprehensibility for the respondents and mitigating potential biases. Consequently, no research survey questionnaire was administered to respondents without prior authorization from the appropriate command channels.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used to treat the data: This determined the extent of the collaborative support system and the teacher's teaching motivation.

Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient of Correlation

This statistical test determined the relationship between the collaborative support system and the teacher's teaching motivation.

Regression

This tool identified the collaborative support system required to enhance the teacher's teaching motivation.

Mean and Standard Deviation

These statistical tools were used to identify the extent of the collaborative support system and the teacher's teaching motivation.

cise record of the team's conversations, decisions made, and planned actions is maintained (4.02). All teachers are provided with ongoing access to these records, including meeting discussions, decisions, and follow-up actions (4.01). Additionally, team dialogue consistently centers on reviewing evidence connected to performance and progress toward goals (4.00). All items under this indicator obtain mean results with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive.

Table 1. The Extent of Collaborative Support System Regarding Dialogue

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Faculty members consistently attend team meetings.	4.03
2.	The agenda for team dialogue is pre-planned, written, and accessible to all teachers before the meeting.	4.02
3.	A thoughtful, thorough, and accurate account of team dialogue, decisions, and intended actions is recorded.	4.02
4.	Every teacher has access to running records of team dialogue, decisions, and subsequent actions to be taken.	4.01
5.	Our dialogue is consistently focused on examining evidence related to performance and the attainment of goals.	4.00
Overall Mean		4.02
		Extensive

This has gained an overall mean of 4.02 with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive with the descriptive equivalent of oftentimes observed which means that the teacher in this indicator was agreed that collaborative dialogue provides opportunities for all task participants to employ language as a cognitive tool to restructure and develop those features of their second language which are not entirely self-regulated. Regardless of proficiency, all learners can benefit from engaging in collaborative dialogue. Classroom Dialogue is a tool that can help students construct knowledge as they explore and build on their own and others’ ideas. This guide is relevant to all teachers of all age groups. The finding parallels Lane’s (2020) point of view that Communication is an art between people. It takes intentional understanding from participants to develop ideas and viewpoints from others. People use a method known as the dialogic circle when talking to others in order to understand someone else. The dialogic circle occurs when two people are involved in the same conversation, each listening to understand instead of responding to each other. This process makes people feel heard and valued for the information they share. Finally, Pentek (2018) asserted that it is essential for classroom teachers and resource specialists to understand each other’s roles in supporting students, so that one

person’s outlook and skill set are not overlooked or given lesser value. Teachers can implement these strategies and foster relationships with one another during their free time or through planned meetings, such as Professional Learning Communities. De Jong et al. (2022) and Lefstein et al. (2020) added that education is a dynamic and ever-evolving field, with teachers playing a pivotal role in shaping future generations. Educators must be committed to continuous learning and continually improve their practices to provide high-quality education. In this context, dialogue among teachers emerges as a powerful tool for reflection, the exchange of ideas, and the evolution of pedagogical strategies to enhance inclusion in educational institutions. Creating an environment where educators can communicate, collaborate, and learn from one another fosters a conducive space for professional growth and educational excellence. Hontvedt et al. (2021) identify dialogue as one of the key phases in these processes and conclude that using techniques such as mutual observation and learning analysis is vital to developing collaboration. They highlight joint planning, peer observation, and reflection as key tasks for this collaboration.

3.2. *The Extent of Collaborative Support System in terms of Decision Making*—Table 2 presented data regarding the extent of the

Collaborative Support System, specifically in the area of decision-making. The items under this indicator were organized according to their mean ratings, listed from highest to lowest. The highest-rated statement was: "The decisions made were clearly and directly related to the improvement of instructional practice and the improvement of student learning," with a mean score of 4.08. The process for making any decision was transparent and adhered to – everyone

knew what the decisions were/were and how and why they were made,(4.07); All of our decisions were informed by group dialogue,(4.00); The team used a specific process for every decision it made, such as consensus,(3.90); and lastly, team members regularly identified specific instructional practices that they would initiate or maintain to increase student learning, (3.89).

Table 2. The Extent of Collaborative Support System in Terms of Decision Making

No.	Statement	Mean
	Descriptive Equivalent	
1.	All of our decisions are informed by group dialogue.	4.00
2.	The process for making any decision is transparent and adhered to – everyone knows what the decisions are/were and how and why they were made.	4.07
3.	The decisions made are clearly and directly related to the improvement of instructional practice and the improvement of student learning.	4.08
4.	The team uses a specific process for every decision, such as consensus.	3.90
5.	Team members regularly identify specific instructional practices that they will initiate or maintain to increase student learning.	3.89
Overall Mean		3.99
		Extensive

This has gained an overall mean of 3.99 with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive with the descriptive equivalent of oftentimes observed which means that the teacher respondents in this indicator have realize that the circumstances that form the setting for an event that would establish the important of work environment that friendly to employee and all people in the organization including the community surrounds the environment that includes the students which are very important client to receive quality services (teaching quality) from the teachers. This finding is congruent with the studies of Obi Obiorah (2023) and Kippers et al. (2018). They asserted that the participation of teachers in school-based decision-

making processes facilitates school leaders' acquisition of the necessary perspectives of staff on the underlying factors contributing to various school-related challenges. Failure to involve teachers in school-based decision-making may hinder the ability to make informed decisions, ultimately affecting the effectiveness of school functions. The existing literature suggests that the active participation of teachers in school decision-making processes is essential for both school and student development. Likewise, the studies of Musengamana et al. (2024), Kilag et al. (2023), and Rwigema and Andala (2022) have articulated that teacher participation in school-based decision-making fosters a belief that the decision-making pro-

cess is collaborative and that every member has a role to play, thereby providing a legitimate and well-supported decision-making process. Active involvement is pivotal in achieving a comprehensive understanding, facilitating adaptability, and effectively implementing decisions. The involvement of individuals in decision-making processes within an organization, such as a school, facilitates their learning and enables them to recognize the organization’s collective goals and objectives. However, Bazirete et al. (2020) anticipate that it will also provide high-quality decisions, incorporating perspectives from individuals inside an organization throughout the decision-making process. Furthermore, these individuals are likely to understand the decisions better and exhibit greater acceptance of them when they have actively

participated. The active involvement of teachers in school decision-making is paramount as it can significantly enhance the educational institution’s overall performance (Denis et al., 2023).

3.3. *The Extent of Collaborative Support System in terms of Action Plan*—Table 3 shows the extent of Collaborative Support regarding the action plan. The presentation is concentrated on the highest, middle, and lowest ratings obtained, namely: Observe and obey all school policy, especially gender-sensitivity and child-centered approach, obtained the highest mean rating (4.05); submit the list of honor students on time two weeks after the quarterly examination, as a median rating (4.00); and use learning strategies and evaluation supported by the school management yielded the lowest mean rating (3.90).

Table 3. The Extent of Collaborative Support System in Terms of Action Plan

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Teachers take actions related to individual/team learning due to team decision-making.	4.00
2.	As a result of group decision-making, teachers make meaningful (pedagogically complex) adjustments to our instructional practice.	4.01
3.	Team member actions are coordinated and interdependent.	3.91
4.	Actions that are taken after or between meetings are distributed equitably among teachers.	3.90
5.	Each member of the team commits to carrying out team actions.	4.05
Overall Mean		3.98
		Extensive

The overall mean of 3.98, with the descriptive equivalent of 'Extensive,' and the descriptive equivalent of 'oftentimes observed,' means that the teacher respondents in this indicator have realized that sometimes we desire to give our best to provide learning to our students. As the most critical work interface, collaboration’s primary goal is to let employees own their responsibilities and perform their work in tandem with their team members. Instead

of working in silos and then meeting to evaluate their work, team members collaborate continuously to make sure they are on the right track. This result aligns with the research conducted by Turner and Sanatana (2023), who examined the "Collaborative Actions to Enhance Effective Teacher Skills in Ban Nong Hua Wua School" project. Their study focused on advancing teachers’ professional development to meet the demands of 21st-century education.

The project incorporated hands-on activities designed to promote collaboration among teachers and to enhance their skills at Ban Nong Hua Wua School. Rosenberg et al. (2020) analyzed four school systems in their work, "Igniting the Learning Engine: How School Systems Accelerate Teacher Effectiveness and Student Growth through Connected Professional Learning," which focused on improving instructional quality through professional development. As a result, these systems achieved superior outcomes, particularly with student populations that have significant needs. These systems had supplanted conventional professional development initiatives, such as isolated workshops and generic coaching, with a more strategic framework that encompassed a rigorous and consistent curriculum, tests, and instructional tools linked to college- and career-ready standards. System administrators ensured that all schools had access to these resources. Content-centric, expert-guided collaboration: Educational leaders assembled educators into teams, directed by subject matter specialists, who were afforded the time, support, and an environment of trust and learning to engage in instructional collaboration and significant joint planning. Regular, growth-focused feedback for educators: Teacher leaders, coaches, or subject matter experts delivered consistent, non-evaluative feedback to teachers to enhance their instructional practices. They stated that these educational systems improved these widely supported, research-backed practices by combin-

This yielded an overall mean rating of 3.82, indicating a high level of motivation efficacy, which was often observed among teachers. All items in this indicator had extensive descriptive ratings. Furthermore, the findings revealed that some respondents agreed that valuing group strengths and weaknesses was a crucial skill for conflict management, as it could help iden-

ing the components into a unified strategy that closely aligns with teachers' daily activities. As a result, we refer to this approach as "Connected Professional Learning." Moving from traditional professional development to Connected Professional Learning requires significant change at both the systemic and school levels. School leaders should ideally utilize comprehensive, standards-based programs and rely on a team of skilled educators dedicated to student growth. However, even under ideal conditions, a common challenge can confuse even the most seasoned principal: "How can we find enough time for meaningful collaborative planning?"

3.4. *The Extent of Collaborative Support System In terms of Evaluation*—Table 4 presents data on the collaborative support system related to evaluation. The focus was on the highest, middle, and lowest mean ratings obtained. During our observations, teachers gathered information about instructional quality, with a mean score of 4.00. Additionally, teachers can clearly and thoroughly describe and provide evidence of their achievements in student learning over time, with a mean of 3.88. The regular sharing of evaluation data on instructional impact within primary teams received a mean rating of 3.87. Observing colleagues' classroom teaching was rated at 3.79. Public recognition of teachers' accomplishments received the lowest mean score among the items at 3.58.

tify areas for improvement, celebrate achievements, and foster collaboration. However, it can also be challenging, as different group members may have varying perspectives, expectations, and preferences. This finding was consistent with Schultes (2023), who reported that evaluation teams gathered fidelity data from students involved in the Reflect program. Addition-

Table 4. The Extent of Collaborative Support System in Terms of Evaluation

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Teachers observe the classroom instruction of our colleagues.	3.79
2.	Teachers collect information on the quality of the instruction during our observation.	4.00
3.	Teachers regularly share evaluation data on the effect of our instruction in our primary team.	3.87
4.	The accomplishments of the teachers are publicly recognized.	3.58
5.	Teachers can accurately and thoroughly articulate and substantiate their accomplishments related to student learning over time.	3.88
Overall Mean		3.82
		Extensive

ally, teachers monitored fidelity through classroom observations and by consistently completing checklists. Outcomes of the intervention were assessed using pre- and post-tests that focused on students’ understanding of gender issues and their occupational aspirations related to gender typicality. The data collected was hierarchical, with students grouped under specific teachers. The evaluation team conducted a multilevel analysis of both intervention and implementation outcomes at the individual student level, as well as fidelity data collected from teachers and classroom observers at the group level. Schultes emphasized that results from implementation evaluations were vital for enhancing school-based interventions. These findings guided evaluators and program developers on how to optimize implementation processes and clarified the relationship between implementation and outcomes of interventions. This approach enabled the refinement and prioritization of essential elements within school-based programs, thereby increasing our understanding of effective interventions and how best to support schools. The evaluation theory tree described by Alkin in *Evaluation Roots* (Chehaib

et al., 2023) focused on increasing the utilization of evaluation through the involvement of stakeholders. A significant amount of collaboration was required between evaluators and key stakeholders for an effective collaborative evaluation. This collaboration had to be carried out to the extent that the stakeholders were willing and able to participate in the evaluation process. To be more specific, collaborative evaluators were responsible for the evaluation, but they also fostered ongoing engagement between the evaluators and the program staff. This engagement led to more robust evaluation designs, improved data collection and analysis, and outcomes that stakeholders could comprehend and utilize (Rodríguez-Campos, cited in Chehaib et al. 2023).

3.5. *Summary of the Collaborative Support System* —Table 5 summarizes the Collaborative Support System, which revealed an overall mean of 3.99. The four indicators were presented with their corresponding mean ratings: Dialogue (4.02), Decision Making (3.99), Action Plan (3.98), and Evaluation (3.82). All four criteria were descriptive equivalents of extensive.

Table 5 summarizes the Collaborative Support System, which revealed an overall mean of 3.99. The four indicators were presented

with their corresponding mean ratings: Dialogue (4.02), Decision Making (3.99), Action Plan (3.98), and Evaluation (3.82). All four cri-

Table 5. Summary of the Collaborative Support System

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Dialogue	4.02	Extensive
Decision Making	3.99	Extensive
Action Plan	3.98	Extensive
Evaluation	3.82	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.99	Extensive

teria were descriptive equivalents of extensive. This finding revealed that the Collaborative Support System in the four indicators obtained a mean rating of 'Extensive', which emphasizes that the respondents in this research were often observed. This further suggested that the work environment was critical for the school to manage, as it motivated teachers to work effectively and encouraged the community to invest by sending their students. The work environment should have been friendly and welcoming to all people in the school. The result corroborated Haight et al. (2024), who noted that collaboration was critical to school-community models of wraparound support (Walker et al., cited in Haight et al., 2024, 2003). Intersectoral school and community partners had to work with families and each other to coordinate support, and if they could not collaborate effectively, this limited the model's impact. However, there was a dearth of research on partnership collaboration in school settings. Accordingly, this study addressed this gap by exploring All in for Youth (AIFY), a collaborative school-community model of wraparound support in a large city in western Canada. Based on discussions with frontline school and community partners, five essential conditions were identified for partnership collaboration, which helped to inform the implementation and operation of similar school models of support and fostered the well-being of children, youth, and families. This result aligns with the findings of Mackenzie (2021), who noted that both classroom teachers and resource specialists often have demand-

ing schedules that require them to support students while meeting core curriculum standards. Effective collaboration between these professionals was crucial for assisting students with disabilities in the classroom. Given the increasing responsibilities teachers faced, there was a pressing need for efficient systems to facilitate collaboration. Mackenzie emphasized that disorganized or ineffective support structures could hinder teachers' efforts to collaborate and communicate effectively. While previous research emphasized the importance of allocating time for teacher collaboration and fostering strong communication and relationships among educators, Mackenzie's study extended this by examining how organized systems—such as technology and administrative support—could have enhanced collaborative efforts when routines were well-structured.

3.6. *The Extent of Teacher Motivation In terms of Welfare*—Table 6 shows the data on the extent of teacher motivation regarding welfare. The presentation of the results focused on the indicators with the ratings ranging from the highest to the lowest, which included participation in functional training, teachers' collective activities, and scientific activities (4.11); salary and bonuses that could meet the needs of teachers (4.01); school holidays and work service credits that had been arranged reasonably (4.00); job satisfaction, including opportunities for career development, support from co-workers, and supervision intensity (3.93); and resource allocation and teaching materials (3.76), which was the lowest among the items.

Table 6. The Extent of Teacher Motivation in Terms of Welfare

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Salary and bonus can meet the needs of teachers.	4.01
2.	School holidays and work service credits have been arranged reasonably.	4.00
3.	Has been relatively allocating resources and teaching materials.	3.76
4.	Job satisfaction, including opportunities for career development, support from co-workers, and supervision intensity.	3.93
5.	Participation in functional training, teachers' collective activities, and scientific activities.	4.11
Overall Mean		3.96
		Extensive

Table 6 shows the data on the extent of teacher motivation regarding welfare. The presentation of the results focused on the indicators with the ratings ranging from the highest to the lowest, which included participation in functional training, teachers' collective activities, and scientific activities (4.11); salary and bonuses that could meet the needs of teachers (4.01); school holidays and work service credits that had been arranged reasonably (4.00); job satisfaction, including opportunities for career development, support from co-workers, and supervision intensity (3.93); and resource allocation and teaching materials (3.76), which was the lowest among the items. This had an overall mean rating of 3.96, indicating that it was often observed. The results suggested that the Extent of Teacher Motivation was crucial in promoting welfare. The study highlighted the importance of such systems in ensuring students remained in school by addressing their comprehensive social, economic, family, and academic needs. It emphasized the necessity of community-wide support to fulfill these requirements, echoing the well-known adage, "It takes a village to raise a child." This finding aligned with the published study by Celestin (2023), who emphasized that staff welfare was a crucial milestone in human resource management within educational insti-

tutions. Schools were supposed to have focused their attention on improved performance to highlight their quality and relevance. Several factors influenced school performance, but this paper focused on the welfare of teachers. Welfare provisions were vital in determining the success of any school because they were one of the bases of staff motivation. For head teachers to manage the performance of teachers, it was critical to conduct a research study to highlight how welfare issues could be better placed within school progress as drivers of performance. Globally, teachers have played a crucial role in promoting societal development (Nkata, cited in Celestin, 2023). In South Africa and Nigeria, teachers are seen as creating sustainable learning environments, advocating for social justice and citizenship (Francis and le Roux, cited in Celestin, 2023). In schools, the teacher was solely responsible for training the child to become a good and 'active' world citizen (Chapin, cited in Celestin, 2023). Teachers determine the quality of a country's education system, especially the extent to which educational products meet societal development requirements. Therefore, teachers had to perform in ways that enhanced positive schooling (UNESCO, as cited in Celestin, 2023).

3.7. *Evaluation and Promotion*—Presented in Table 7 were data on the extent of teacher motivation in terms of Evaluation and Promotion. The presentation concentrated on the indicators with the ratings obtained from highest to lowest: the current assessment mea-

asures could help teachers reflect and improve had the highest mean rating (4.09); post arrangement policies could enable teachers to give full play to their talents had the median rating (4.00); and encouraging teachers to work hard to achieve their desired goals in the school organization had the lowest mean rating (3.98).

Table 7. The Extent of Teacher Motivation in Terms of Evaluation and Promotion

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Current assessment measures can help teachers reflect and improve.	4.09
2.	The professional title evaluation system can make teachers feel full of work motivation.	3.99
3.	Post arrangement policy can enable teachers to give full play to their talents.	4.00
4.	Please encourage them to work hard to achieve their desired goal in the school organization.	3.98
5.	Increase their interest or motivation for professional growth and development to support students' learning needs.	4.01
Overall Mean		4.01
		Extensive

Collectively, the overall mean of 4.01, with a descriptive equivalent of "Extensive," indicated that evaluation and promotion were often observed. The results suggested that evaluating and promoting classroom collaboration involved assessing how effectively students worked together in groups, including their communication skills, active participation, conflict resolution, and individual contributions, while implementing strategies to encourage and develop these collaborative behaviors within the classroom environment. This result was consistent with Heathfield (2018), who explained that promotion within an organization represented an employee's progression to a higher position, reflecting changes in status, rank, or role. Such advancement was considered a form of internal human resource mobility. Positions for office-based promotions were typically announced through Human Resource Circulars distributed to all schools and educational in-

stitutions in the province, as well as through postings on the provincial website and in local newspapers. Supporting this, Mbokazi et al. (2022) noted that opportunities for promotion contributed to educators' personal growth, increased engagement, and greater job satisfaction within the department. Similarly, Ekabu et al. (2018) agreed that promotion prospects led to higher salaries for educators, enhanced job satisfaction, and encouraged staff retention. Additionally, Benjamin and Ahmad, as cited in Mbokazi et al. (2022), found that factors such as financial incentives, promotional opportunities, career development, and recognition were crucial in retaining employees. They further suggested that creating promotion posts could improve job quality and performance. Therefore, it was important for organizations to promote individuals who were qualified, experienced, knowledgeable, and skilled in order to fulfill job requirements effectively.

3.8. *Growth Support*—Table 8 presented results related to Teacher Motivation concerning growth support. The items under this indicator were ranked in order of their mean ratings, from highest to lowest. The statement "work was organized, goals were clearly defined, and responsibilities were specified" received the highest mean score of 4.05, followed by "a comprehensive professional development plan for teachers

had been developed," which had a mean rating of 4.04; arranged the work, and the workload was allocated reasonably, with a mean of 4.03; had complete and advanced hardware and software for work, with a mean of 4.01; and gave teachers relatively full autonomy in their work, which had the lowest mean rating of 3.97. All items under this indicator yielded mean results with descriptive equivalents that were often observed.

Table 8. Teacher Motivation in Terms of Growth Support

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Has complete and advanced hardware and software for work.	4.01
2.	Has formulated a detailed professional development plan for teachers.	4.04
3.	Arranges the work, and the workload is allocated reasonably.	4.03
4.	Arranges the work, the goal is clear, and the responsibility is specific.	4.05
5.	Gives teachers relatively full autonomy in their work.	3.97
Overall Mean		4.02
		Extensive

This had gained an overall mean of 4.02, with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive and the descriptive equivalent of oftentimes observed, which meant that the teacher believed collaboration was crucial for growth support because it allowed teachers to pool their knowledge, skills, and perspectives, leading to more innovative solutions, improved problem-solving, and ultimately, more remarkable progress and development in any field or organization; essentially, by working together, individuals could achieve more than they could alone, driving personal and collective growth. This finding was confirmed by Keiler (2018), who recognized the importance of student-centered pedagogy in facilitating effective learning. However, a significant research gap remained in understanding the intricate mechanism by which student-centered pedagogy was most effectively integrated into

school education to achieve desirable student outcomes. Similarly, Bremner et al. (2022) noted that a notable absence is the lack of a thorough examination of how student-centered pedagogy affects students' cognitive learning processes and, consequently, their cognitive abilities, considering the multilayered dynamics of the school environment. School activities occur at different levels in education, and the evaluation of school mechanisms should be delineated using multilevel approaches. As suggested by Alonso-Tapia and Ruiz-Díaz (2022), classroom dynamics were shaped by student attributes and the characteristics of teachers and schools, suggesting an interplay between multilayered factors in education. Until now, most multilevel studies in education have focused on two levels of analysis, investigating teacher- and student-level influences. In a practical sense, students are nested within teachers and classes, which

are further nested within schools.

3.9. *Cultural Atmosphere*—As shown in Table 9, the data on the Collaborative Support System, in terms of the Cultural Atmosphere, were arranged logically, from the highest to the lowest ratings. Can promote mutual care and appreciation among teachers was the highest mean rating, (4.07); can promote teachers’ teamwork and democratic participation in management, (4.03); providing support, training,

and professional development opportunities to educators, (4.01); teachers also encouraged to acknowledge one another’s contributions, which received a mean score of 3.99. The statement regarding the positive environment created by various school competitions and evaluation activities had the lowest mean rating at 3.96. was the lowest mean rating. All items under this indicator yield mean results with descriptive equivalents that are often observed.

Table 9. Teacher Motivation in Terms of Cultural Atmosphere

No.	Statement	Mean
Descriptive Equivalent		
1.	Can promote teachers’ teamwork and democratic participation in management.	4.03
2.	Can promote mutual care and appreciation among teachers.	4.07
3.	Can encourage teachers to recognize each other’s efforts in their work.	3.99
4.	Providing support, training, and professional development opportunities to educators.	4.01
5.	The competitive atmosphere of various competitions and evaluation activities in the school is good.	3.96
Overall Mean		4.01
		Extensive

This has yielded an overall mean of 4.01, indicating an extensive understanding, with the descriptive equivalent of ‘often observed’, which suggests that the teacher fully appreciates the importance of a cultural atmosphere in creating an ideal workplace for teaching and learning. A vibrant cultural atmosphere influences how individuals interact, communicate, and behave within a community. It nurtures a deep sense of belonging, fosters mutual understanding, and sparks creativity and innovation by establishing a common foundation of values, beliefs, and practices. Essentially, it weaves the threads of social cohesion within a group, ultimately enhancing overall well-being and productivity within that environment. This finding was supported by literature indicating that culture often operates beneath the surface and exerts a powerful yet subtle influence within organiza-

tions (Abu-Jarad, Yusof, Nikbin, as cited in Ismail, Khatibi, and Azam, 2022). Culture encompasses shared beliefs, norms, and values that shape the behaviors of organizational members (Ali, Sharma, Zaman, as referenced in Ismail et al., 2022). Each school develops its own traditions and beliefs, which are shaped by the attitudes and relationships among its members. According to Peterson as cited in Ismail et al. (2022), school culture affects the way individuals think, feel, and behaved. A positive school culture can enhance all aspects of school functioning, including overall effectiveness. Despite this, culture was not always recognized as a primary factor in school effectiveness, as educational challenges were often viewed through the lens of educational psychology, with a focus on classroom methods and environments (Manaf Omar, cited in Ismail et

al., 2022; Widodo, 2019). These conclusions were consistent with the work of Dimmock et al. (2021), who emphasized that education plays a vital role in shaping individuals within a community. Educational institutions are responsible for delivering high-quality education to prepare students for future challenges, and schools are expected to provide environments that support the development of essential skills and knowledge. Each organization, shaped by its mission and objectives, develops unique characteristics, including its own culture. School culture was a key component that adds value and meaning to various school activities. Ismail et al. (2022) further described school culture as the core identity of an institution, shaped by the collective values, norms, beliefs, and traditions of its members.

This culture can foster an effective environment for teaching and learning while strengthening relationships among staff and the broader institution. As such, school culture was considered a crucial factor in achieving school effectiveness.

3.10. The Summary of the Extent of Teacher Motivation —Table 10 presents data on the Summary of the Extent of Teacher Motivation. The overall mean of 4.00 is extensive or often observed, which is distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: Welfare (3.96), Evaluation and Promotion (4.01), Growth Support (4.02), and Cultural Atmosphere (4.01). All of these indicators have the descriptive equivalent of Extensive.

Table 10. The Summary of the Extent of Teacher Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Welfare	3.96	Extensive
Evaluation and Promotion	4.01	Extensive
Growth Support	4.02	Extensive
Cultural Atmosphere	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.00	Extensive

This finding reveals that teacher motivation was crucial because it directly impacts the quality of teaching, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes; a motivated teacher was more likely to be enthusiastic, creative, and dedicated to their students, fostering a positive learning environment and inspiring students to achieve their full potential; conversely, unmotivated teachers can lead to disengaged students and lower academic performance. Support for this finding can be found in the work of Özbilen et al. (2020) and Sari and Yetkiner (2020), who argue that highly motivated teachers are essential for ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of the educational process. They

highlight teacher motivation as a key aspect of teacher quality, playing a vital role in inspiring students to learn, implementing educational reforms, and achieving teacher satisfaction. Furthermore, teacher motivation has a direct impact on job performance. This perspective was consistent with Julião (2018), who noted that motivated teachers are instrumental in shaping and updating national education curricula to meet current needs. A centrally designed curriculum can help bridge the gap between teachers' educational objectives and the actual learning needs of students. Teachers are also responsible for adapting curriculum elements to address local learning requirements. As Julião points

out, teachers play a crucial part in managing and tailoring educational processes, making the curriculum effective regardless of the prevailing educational paradigm. Therefore, it is important to have teachers who can adapt the central curriculum using the principles of curriculum autonomy, combined with critical and relational skills appropriate to local conditions and student needs. Greater autonomy in handling the curriculum can enhance teachers' motivation to participate in school activities. Thus, when considering factors such as curriculum autonomy, motivated teachers were better equipped to deliver high-quality education.

Additionally, Zhang, Admiraal, and Saab (2021) explained that teachers' personal and psychological traits, along with their perceptions of workplace conditions, can significantly affect their motivation to engage in profes-

sional learning. McMillan, McConnell, and O'Sullivan have developed a model, as referenced by Zhang et al. (2021), that outlines various factors influencing teachers' motivation to participate in professional development activities. This approach offers an exhaustive perspective on the motivating and demotivating elements influencing teachers' motivation for ongoing professional growth across three dimensions: personal, institutional, and systemic. Factors at these three levels can either promote or limit instructors' autonomous and controlled desire to engage in learning activities.

3.11. Relationship between Collaborative Support System and Teacher Motivation—It can be inferred that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between the collaborative support system ($r = 0.8297$; $p < .001$) and teachers' teaching motivation

Table 11. Significant Relationship between the Collaborative Support System and the Teachers' Motivation

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Teachers' motivation	0.8297	< 0.001	Significant	Reject H0

Note: *Significant

at $p < 0.05$.

Table 11 revealed the significant correlation between the collaborative support system and teachers' teaching motivation. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis, stating there was no significant relationship between collaborative support systems and teachers' teaching motivation, must be rejected, as the results provide empirical evidence of significant findings. Teachers' motivation was crucial because it directly impacts student learning. Motivated teachers were more likely to be engaged, enthusiastic, and dedicated to their students' success, thereby creating a positive learning environment and fostering better student outcomes. Conversely, unmotivated teachers can lead to disengagement and lower student achievement. On the other hand, a Collaborative

Support System was important because it allows individuals or teams to work together effectively by sharing information, expertise, and resources. This leads to improved problem-solving, better decision-making, increased productivity, and a stronger sense of community, especially when tackling complex challenges that require diverse perspectives and coordinated efforts. This research indicates a strong positive correlation between a collaborative support system and teacher motivation, meaning that when teachers have access to a supportive network where they can collaborate with peers, their overall motivation to teach tends to increase significantly; this was because collaboration fosters a sense of community, shared responsibility, and professional development opportunities, leading to

higher levels of job satisfaction and efficacy. Ahn et al. (2021) found a link between teacher motivation and practices that support students' needs. Teachers who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to employ instructional methods that cater to students' psychological needs, particularly by fostering autonomy. Students often perceive these teachers as fostering autonomy and expressing a preference for such approaches. Additionally, these teachers are generally seen as supportive of students' sense of belonging and providing clear guidance (Abos et al., 2018). In contrast, teachers driven by external pressures are viewed as offering less autonomy, structure, and engagement. Research has yet to explore all the key connections between different types of teacher motivation and various need-supportive practices within a single study, which this research aims to address.

According to Kolleck (2019), teacher collaboration was a fundamental component in numerous school improvement efforts, professional development programs, and educational policies internationally, given its proven significance. For example, the National Staff Development Council, established in 1969 to promote educational advancement in the United States, recognized teacher collaboration as one of its twelve standards for effective staff development. Moreover, collaboration has been reinforced through policy initiatives such as the creation of "learning communities."

3.12. Domains of Collaborative Support System That Significantly Influences Teachers' Motivation—Table 12 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis of the domains of the Collaborative Support System that significantly influence the teachers' Motivation.

Table 12. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Collaborative Support Systems That Significantly Influence Teachers' Motivation

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decision	
H	(Intercept)	4.397	0.062	< 0.001	Reject Null	
H	(Intercept)	0.401	0.144	0.006	Reject Null	
	Dialogue	0.032	-0.021	0.066	0.001	Reject Null
	Decision Making	0.342	0.361	0.084	0.010	Reject Null
	Action	0.207	0.215	0.094	0.002	Reject Null
	Evaluation	0.568	0.415	0.089	0.001	Reject Null
R²				0.889		
F-value				225.796		
p-value				< 0.002		

Table 12 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis of the domains of the Collaborative Support System that significantly influence the teachers' Motivation. All collaborative support system components that significantly influence the value formation among learners in terms of dialogue (p = 0.001), decision-making (p = 0.010), action (p = 0.002), and evaluation (p = 0.001) were statistically significant in terms of teachers' motivation. This shows that the

teachers' Motivation for the Collaborative Support System domains significantly influences learners' values formation. In every unit determined by Beta, the same value will be used for each increase of the influences on the dependent variable. The R² value of 0.889 indicates that collaborative support systems account for 88.9 percent of the variation in teacher motivation. This finding offers empirical support for the significant role that these support system domains

play in influencing teacher motivation. Furthermore, the F-value, which represents the ratio of explained variance (model) to unexplained variance (error), was 225.796 and statistically significant at $p < .002$. This suggests that the model provides a strong prediction of teacher motivation. Teachers' motivation was a crucial aspect of education that aims to develop learners' positive attitudes and values, enabling them to become responsible members of society. The components of a collaborative support system, including dialogue, Decision-making, action, and evaluation, have been identified as significant predictors that directly influence teachers' motivations. A teacher's motivation was crucial in a collaborative system because it directly impacts the effectiveness of teamwork, knowledge sharing, and overall positive outcomes within the collaborative environment; when teachers feel motivated to collaborate, they were more likely to actively participate, share ideas, and support their colleagues, leading to improved learning experiences for students and a more productive working environment for everyone involved.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the research's focal points and the statistical interpretation results. The study concludes with findings and corresponding recommendations. This study aimed to determine the relationship between the collaborative support system and teacher teaching motivation in public elementary schools in the Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The Collaborative Support System was presented with the corresponding mean: Dialogue, Decision Making, Action Plan, and Evaluation. All of these indicators are descriptive equivalents of Extensive. This finding suggests that the Collaborative Support System encountered by the study respondents indicates that the availability of variables was a priority for the school, as the Collaborative Support System has been proven to address some research gaps in all aspects of research based on their previous work experiences. Teacher motivation was important in a learning environment; a teacher's motivation can cause students to engage or disengage. A student's motivation may be driven by either intrinsic or extrinsic factors for teachers. Furthermore, fostering motivation in teachers and students can benefit them as they navigate their lives. This reveals that the teacher, who emphasized the four indicators of motivation, often observed that the respondents in this research were at an extensive level in Welfare, Promotion, Growth Support, and Cultural Atmosphere.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions were drawn: The extent of the collaborative support system, encompassing dialogue, decision-making, action plans, and evaluation, was extensive. The extent of a collaborative support system allows for a shared understanding of an individual's needs, promotes open communication between different support providers, and leverages diverse perspectives to create more comprehensive and practical solutions, ultimately leading to better outcomes for the person being supported, whether in a community, workplace, or educational setting. It is an institutional strategy to achieve a greater goal in the school, which was high academic performance. The extent of the teacher's teaching motivation, in terms of Welfare, Promotion, Growth Support, and cultural atmosphere, was also extensive. The work environment was perceived as essential in the school community. Meanwhile, teacher efficacy was extensive in terms of motivation, student performance, reinforcement, and persistence. Significant rela-

tionships exist between collaborative support systems and teachers' motivation to teach in public elementary schools in Laak North District, Davao de Oro, Philippines. All domains under the collaborative support system substantially impacted teachers' motivation to teach. The elements of a collaborative support system were dialogue, decision-making, action, and evaluation. The results concerning collaborative support networks were unequivocally associated with teachers' motivation, as outlined in Bandura's theory of self-efficacy. Bandura's theory posits that self-efficacy, a teacher's belief in their ability to succeed, has a significant influence on their motivation and behavior. Collaborative support, encompassing peer mentoring and professional development focused on teamwork, can augment teachers' self-efficacy by providing vicarious experiences (observing others' successes), verbal persuasion (receiving encouragement), and mastery experiences (achieving success in collaborative endeavors). Such experiences can bolster teachers' confidence in addressing educational challenges, leading to increased motivation and a more positive outlook. Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory posits that individuals' confidence in their abilities has a significant impact on their choices, effort, persistence, and overall performance. Collaborative support among educators is an essential source of self-efficacy, as teamwork enables them to gain new ideas, observe effective practices, receive constructive feedback, and achieve favorable results from collaboration. This increased confidence cultivates greater drive, encouraging educators to tackle challenging tasks, withstand difficulties, and pursue continuous development. Examples of collaborative support include peer observation, team teaching, professional learning communities, and mentorship programs. Studies indicate that educators who have significant collaborative assistance display enhanced self-efficacy and motivation. Research indicates that colleague support was positively associ-

ated with improvements in self-efficacy. In contrast, collaborative activities, such as peer talks and microteaching, strengthen the self-efficacy views of non-native student instructors. Another area of motivation research explores the locus of control phenomenon. The concept of locus of control was a subject of ongoing research in the field of motivation. This hypothesis asserts that individuals are more driven when they regard themselves as having control over their achievements and failures (Eccles Wigfield). One version of control theory asserts that autonomy was one of the three fundamental psychological needs, alongside competence and relatedness.

4.2. Recommendations—Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered for consideration: The school administration should cooperate with and assess the classroom teachers to create a harmonious and conducive learning environment, which is a key component of a successful school in education. They may also request the DepEd to organize or design a seminar for teachers on establishing a collaborative support system at the school level, as part of the school-based management system. They may be informed about the results of this study, especially the effective indicators in collaborative support systems and teacher teaching motivation, as these are critically important to teacher efficacy. Teachers can maintain high teaching motivation to facilitate effective classroom learning and ensure students' success in their schooling. Teachers may be positive and know how to encourage students to show their talents and abilities. Teachers may encourage their students to participate in the course and share their ideas. The teacher should provide day-to-day situations that are as desirable as possible, so that the student's interest grows and they become motivated to develop in areas that align with the teacher's and student's goals. Individuals were motivated by their own needs and desires. The psychological and physical conditions that address these needs can mo-

tivate students to respond. Likewise, they may continue to cooperate with Department of Education programs, especially those that can enhance their supervisory skills. Lastly, a similar or comparative study exploring other indicators was suggested to develop a collaborative support system, teacher teaching motivation, and publish this study in a reputable journal.

5. References

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